

Is Shortest Always Best?

The Role of Brevity in Logic-to-Text Generation

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Abstract

Some applications of artificial intelligence make it desirable that logical formulae be converted computationally to comprehensible natural language sentences. As there are many logical equivalents to a given formula, finding the most suitable equivalent to be used as input for such a “logic-to-text” generation system is a difficult challenge. In this paper, we focus on the role of brevity: Are the shortest formulae the most suitable? We focus on propositional logic (PL), framing formula minimization (i.e., the problem of finding the shortest equivalent of a given formula) as a Quantified Boolean Formulae (QBFs) satisfiability problem. We experiment with several generators and selection strategies to prune the resulting candidates. We conduct exhaustive automatic and human evaluations of the comprehensibility and fluency of the generated texts. The results suggest that while, in many cases, minimization has a positive impact on the quality of the sentences generated, formula minimization may ultimately not be the best strategy.

<https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/eduardo.calo/brevity-PL>

1 Introduction

Logical formulae (LFs) are essential for scholars in many scientific fields, such as artificial intelligence and linguistics (e.g., formal semantics). For instance, some explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) methods (e.g., Guidotti et al., 2018) use LFs to provide interpretable and faithful explanations to black-box models. However, one of the drawbacks of these XAI methods is that their output formulae might be complex, hindering their understandability. Grasping the meaning of formulae is also hard for students of logic, especially when they are exposed to formalisms they are not yet accustomed to (Rector et al., 2004). Natural language generation

(NLG) methods can be employed to simplify and translate LFs into understandable text in natural languages (NLs), effectively providing explanations for them.

Recently, NLG has made remarkable progress. In particular, in the context of data-to-text generation, good results have been achieved in different domains and datasets, such as sport (e.g., the ROTOWIRE dataset (Wiseman et al., 2017; Thomson et al., 2020)), restaurant (e.g., the E2E Challenge (Smiley et al., 2018; Dušek et al., 2020)), or WebNLG (Gardent et al., 2017). However, the texts produced in these contexts are often relatively poor in logical and rhetorical structure. Moreover, neural language models still fail to encode the semantics of logical formulae (Traylor et al., 2021b) and acquire analytical and deductive logical reasoning capabilities (Ryb et al., 2022). In particular, they struggle with logical connectives, where they fail to differentiate between conjunction and disjunction (Traylor et al., 2021a). Logic-to-text generation thus addresses an area of natural language processing where further progress is much needed.

One way in which the task of generating NL from complex LFs could be facilitated is by simplifying the input. We are interested in understanding the factors that make a formula more or less suitable as an input for a generator. In our work, we focus on brevity. The concept of brevity has long been a topic of linguistic discussion, dating back to at least Grice (1975), where Grice’s submaxim of brevity states that shorter utterances should be favored over longer ones, avoiding unnecessary verbosity. Brevity has loomed large in computational accounts of language use as well, especially in the modeling of the human production of referring expressions (see §6 for discussion), a research area known as referring expressions generation (REG). Brevity could also be useful in our situation, in which case a shorter formula, instead of a lengthier logical equivalent, once verbalized using an NLG

algorithm, might lead to NL sentences that are more fluent and easier to understand.

In this paper, we study the role of brevity in logic-to-text generation, focusing on propositional logic (PL), a formalism for which logical equivalence is decidable. We formulate propositional logic formula minimization (i.e., finding the shortest logical equivalent of a given formula) as a Quantified Boolean Formulae (QBFs) satisfiability problem and employ the algorithm introduced in Calò and Levy (2023) that consistently identifies the shortest equivalents for a given formula.

It is not a foregone conclusion that the shortest formula must always lead to the best verbalization in English. To see this, suppose the input to the generator is of the form $\neg p \vee \neg q$. If the Sheffer stroke, $|$, (i.e., the NAND operator) is a permitted symbol, then the same information can be written more briefly as $p|q$, yet a “direct” verbalization of the former formula (e.g., *Not p or not q*) could well be more comprehensible and fluent than a direct verbalization of the latter (e.g., *It is not the case that p and q*), because the Sheffer stroke does not have a convenient shorthand in English.

Following this line of thought, several questions arise: When verbalizing an input logical formula into English, is it useful to start by finding the shortest formula that is equivalent to the input? Is the resulting text comprehensible to humans? How do we choose among the pool of potential shortest equivalent candidates?

The last question specifically opens up the issue of selecting the optimal translation, given that all potential shortest candidates are exactly of the same length. In our work, we experiment with several deterministic rule-based generators (thus controlling for faithfulness) and a number of selection strategies based on linguistic criteria, ranging from heuristics to neural metrics, to prune the resulting NL candidates. Finally, we conduct comprehensive automatic and human evaluations to assess comprehensibility and fluency of the generated texts.

2 Background

Logical Optimization Extensive research has been conducted on optimizing complex Boolean expressions, particularly in the field of electronic circuits, where practical considerations (i.e., a more complicated circuit with more logic gates takes up more physical space and produces more heat) make it paramount to find the smallest possible circuit,

and hence the shortest possible (i.e., “minimal”) formula representing its content. Popular methods for minimization include the Quine-McCluskey algorithm (Quine, 1952, 1955; McCluskey, 1956), Karnaugh maps (Karnaugh, 1953), the Petrick’s method (Petrick, 1956), and the Espresso heuristic logic minimizer (Brayton et al., 1982). However, most work has focused on a limited set of canonical forms, such as conjunctive normal form (CNF) or disjunctive normal form (DNF). For our purposes (i.e., studying the interactions between logic and language), we need a general approach where a larger set of connectives and a wider variety of logical structures can be taken into account.

Quantified Boolean Formulae Quantified Boolean Formulae (QBFs) are an extension of propositional logic, where universal and existential quantifications over Boolean variables are allowed (Kleine Büning and Bubeck, 2009). Any QBF ϕ can be rewritten in a canonical prenex conjunctive normal form (PCNF) without any loss in expressivity, as follows. Let \mathcal{B} be a finite set of Boolean variables, and $\mathcal{Q} = \{\forall, \exists\}$. A QBF ϕ over \mathcal{B} in PCNF is given by $\phi := Q_1 B_1 . Q_2 B_2 \dots Q_n B_n . \psi$, where $Q_i \in \mathcal{Q}$, $B_i \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, and ψ is a Boolean formula over \mathcal{B} in CNF. The part including only quantifiers and bound variables $Q_1 B_1 . Q_2 B_2 \dots Q_n B_n$ is called the *prefix*, and ψ is called the *matrix*.

The QBF satisfiability problem (Giunchiglia et al., 2009) involves determining the truth of a given QBF ϕ . For example, given the QBF $\phi := \exists x_1, \dots, x_n . \forall y_1, \dots, y_m . \exists z_1, \dots, z_t . \psi$, ϕ is true iff, there exists a truth assignment to x_1, \dots, x_n , such that, for all truth assignments to y_1, \dots, y_m , there exists a truth assignment to z_1, \dots, z_t such that ψ is true. To solve this problem, several QBF solvers have been developed.¹ Practical applications of QBFs include AI, logic, planning, and games (Cashmore and Fox, 2010; Diptarama and Shinohara, 2016; Shukla et al., 2019). In our study, we utilize QBFs to encode and solve PL formula minimization.

Logic-to-Text Generation Logic-to-text generation is the task of generating NL text, starting from a logical formalism (e.g., propositional logic, description logic, or first-order logic). Although the bulk of recent work on NLG (see e.g., Gatt and Krahmer (2018) for a survey) has focused on other areas, generating text from logic nonetheless

¹<http://www.qbflib.org>

has a long tradition, with approaches ranging from rule-based methodologies (Wang, 1980; De Roeck and Lowden, 1986; Calder et al., 1989; Shieber et al., 1989; Shemtov, 1996; Carroll and Oepen, 2005; Mpagouli and Hatzilygeroudis, 2009; Coppock and Baxter, 2010; Butler, 2016; Flickinger, 2016; Kasenberg et al., 2019) to statistical (Wong and Mooney, 2007; Lu and Ng, 2011; Basile, 2015) and neural models (Manome et al., 2018; Hajdik et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2022).

One of the complicating factors for this task is the problem of *logical-form equivalence* (Appelt, 1987; Shieber, 1988, 1993), which implies that every logical formula is equivalent to infinitely many other formulae, where the question of whether two formulae are logically equivalent is, in many formalisms (e.g., first-order logic), undecidable. In the present paper, we circumvent this problem by focusing on a decidable fragment of logic, as did, e.g., van Deemter and Halldórsson (2001) and Minock (2014) before us in different ways.

In a closely related work, Calò et al. (2022) manipulate a given first-order formula to obtain logically equivalent simplified versions via logical equivalence laws, yet their algorithm is not guaranteed to return the shortest formula.

3 Algorithm

To solve our PL minimization problem, we leverage the QBF-based algorithm presented in Calò and Levy (2023). We define formula length as the number of symbols (i.e., predicates and connectives, parentheses excluded) contained in a formula.

In outline, given (i) a PL formula ψ and (ii) a functionally complete set \mathcal{C} of PL connectives, the algorithm produces the set $\mathcal{P} = \{\psi'_1, \dots, \psi'_n\}$ of all those PL formulae such that (a) ψ and ψ'_i are logically equivalent, (b) ψ'_i does not contain any connectives that are not members of \mathcal{C} , and (c) there does not exist any strictly shorter sentence χ satisfying (a) and (b).

The strength of the QBF-based algorithm is that it computes a *scheme* T_n of all candidates ψ'_i of length n , instead of checking each one of ψ'_i for equivalence with ψ . Tseitin transformation (Tseitin, 1983) is used to encode the equivalence of T_n and ψ as a QBF formula, which is checked for satisfiability (see Section 2) by a QBF solver (Tentrup, 2019). The algorithm can find all $\psi'_i \in \mathcal{P}$ of a certain length n . By making several calls to

the QBF solver, increasing n , we make sure that the first found solution is a minimal solution.

The fact that the algorithm computes a unique *scheme* for all candidates of length n makes it very efficient, compared with other straightforward approaches. We refer the reader to Calò and Levy (2023) for details on the implementation.

4 Experiments

Our experimentation strategy can be summarized as follows: (i) we simplify the input formulae using the algorithm described in §3, (ii) we realize all the outputs using different generators, and (iii) we prune the resulting candidate realizations using a number of selection strategies.

We use three rule-based generators: (i) a BASELINE, (ii) the system presented in Ranta (2011), and (iii) LOLA (Calò et al., 2022). BASELINE is a system that generates near-literal translations of the formulae. Ranta performs some syntactic optimization (e.g., flattening, aggregation, etc.) to improve fluency. LOLA is an extension of Ranta that performs heuristic logical optimization based on standard equivalence laws to the input formula before verbalizing it. The generators were evaluated for faithfulness (i.e., whether the generated text conveys all and only the information of the input formula) in Calò et al. (2022) and shown to guarantee faithful translations. We refer the reader to Ranta (2011) and Calò et al. (2022) for more details on the systems.

For pruning, we experiment with the following five selection strategies: (i) length in number of words, (ii) pseudo-perplexity using BERT (Devlin et al., 2019), (iii) pseudo-SLOR using BERT, (iv) perplexity (PPL) using GPT-2 (Radford et al., 2019), (v) SLOR using GPT-2.² SLOR (Syntactic Log-Odds Ratio; Pauls and Klein, 2012; Kann et al., 2018) is a metric based on negative log-likelihood that penalizes highly probable unigrams. In detail, the score given by SLOR consists of the log probability of a sentence under a given language model, normalized by unigram log probability and sentence length. The intuition behind the normalizations is that a rare token should not bring down the sentence’s score and shorter sentences should not be preferred over equally fluent longer ones. In our case, this should help us make fairer comparisons, as the length of the sentences generated by the re-

²We use bert-large-cased and gpt-2-large, respectively.

alizers varies considerably, and logical variables and constants (e.g., x , y , etc., which a language model treats as unigrams), which appear regularly in our sentences, have a unigram probability much higher than the other tokens in the lexicon. We compute PPL and SLOR with BERT, following the methodologies described in Salazar et al. (2020) and Lau et al. (2020) for masked language models.

For the experiments, we consider the Grade Grinder Corpus (GGC; Barker-Plummer et al., 2011), a parallel corpus where each NL sentence is paired with multiple logically equivalent formulae. We retrieve all PL formulae that are parsable by the generators we use. We first simplify the formulae using the algorithm described in §3 and obtain, for each formula, a set of logical equivalents, maximally reduced in terms of length. Out of 1092 PL formulae, 680 got simplified; the others were already in their shortest form. Table 1 shows some descriptive statistics. As a concrete example, starting from the following GGC formula containing 10 symbols:

$$(Tet(a) \wedge Tet(c)) \rightarrow \neg(\neg Large(a) \wedge \neg Large(c))$$

we end up with these shortest equivalents, with the number of symbols reduced to 7:³

$$\begin{aligned} & Large(a) \vee ((Tet(c) \wedge Tet(a)) \rightarrow Large(c)) \\ & (Tet(c) \rightarrow Large(c)) \vee (Tet(a) \rightarrow Large(a)) \\ & (Tet(c) \wedge Tet(a)) \rightarrow (Large(c) \vee Large(a)) \\ & \dots \end{aligned}$$

	μ	σ	Min.	Max.
Original	7.12	2.62	1	18
Minimized	5.52	1.97	1	11

Table 1: Statistics on the length of the GGC formulae before and after minimization.

We proceed with translating the resulting formulae into English using the three rule-based generators. Additionally, we also translate the original GGC formula with the three generators.

At the logic level, all potential candidates are exactly of the same length. Therefore, once NL sentences are generated, we prune the candidates by (i) scoring them using the five selection strategies

³We list just some of the equivalents, as the algorithm returns many more formulae of length 7 in the actual output.

mentioned above, (ii) selecting the one with the lowest score for each strategy. After this process, for each GGC input formula, we end up with 18 realizations: 15 after the pruning process (3 realizers \times 5 selection strategies), plus 3 from translating the original GGC formula with the three realizers. Table 2 presents some examples.

5 Evaluation

5.1 Automatic Evaluation

We set up an automatic evaluation comparing the translations by the 18 systems presented in §4 vs. the ground truth NL references associated with the original input formulae in the GGC. We use six automatic metrics, three of which are based on n -gram overlap, namely, BLEU (Papineni et al., 2002),⁴ METEOR (Banerjee and Lavie, 2005), and ROUGE-L (Lin, 2004), and three on BERT, namely, BERTScore (Zhang et al., 2020),⁵ BLEURT (Sellam et al., 2020), a learned metric based on human ratings,⁶ and SBERT (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019).⁷ For all the metrics except SBERT, we use the implementations provided by HuggingFace (Wolf et al., 2020).⁸ Table 3 summarizes the results obtained.

Several trends emerge from analyzing the table. The results hint that formula minimization generally improves the translations, as the scores (particularly n -gram-based metrics) for the systems that get the minimized versions of the formulae as input are generally higher than the others. Different selection strategies score very similarly, sometimes with negligible differences. The difference in behavior between semantics-based and n -gram-based metrics corroborates the findings in Calò et al. (2022). Excluding BLEURT, whose low results are probably due to the nature of the data on which it was pre-trained and the lack of fine-tuning on our side, the results of semantics-based metrics are comparable across the systems, especially when it comes to BERTScore. This can be seen as a confirmation that the generated texts are paraphrases of the GGC ground truth references. However, BERTScore’s results need to be taken with a grain of salt, since BERT-like models are known for missing semantic

⁴We adopt the SacreBLEU (Post, 2018) implementation for improved reproducibility.

⁵We use the model roberta-large_L17_no-idf.

⁶We use the model bleurt-base-128 without fine-tuning.

⁷We compute cosine similarity after obtaining sentence embeddings with the model all-distilroberta-v1.

⁸<https://huggingface.co/evaluate-metric>

System + Selection Strategy	Translation
Orig. BASELINE	<i>If f is large, then f is a cube or if f is large, then f is a dodecahedron.</i>
Orig. Ranta	<i>At least one of these holds: - if f is large, then f is a cube - if f is large, then f is a dodecahedron.</i>
Orig. LOLA	<i>f is not large, f is a cube, f is not large or f is a dodecahedron.</i>
Minim. BASELINE BERT SLOR	<i>f is a dodecahedron or if f is large, then f is a cube.</i>
Minim. Ranta GPT PPL	<i>If f is large, then f is a cube or f is a dodecahedron.</i>
Minim. LOLA Length	<i>f is not large, f is a cube or f is a dodecahedron.</i>

Table 2: Some translations from the original formula $(Large(f) \rightarrow Cube(f)) \vee (Large(f) \rightarrow Dodec(f))$.

System + Selection Strategy	n -gram-based Metrics			Semantics-based Metrics		
	METEOR	ROUGE-L	SacreBLEU	BERTScore	BLEURT	SBERT
Orig. BASELINE	0.5514	0.4386	10.8638	0.9051	-0.0916	0.7819
Orig. Ranta	0.5654	0.4697	12.1577	0.9082	-0.1099	0.7464
Orig. LOLA	0.5655	0.5012	14.0046	0.9115	-0.0492	0.7672
Minim. BASELINE Length	0.5639	0.4955	14.7115	0.9129	-0.0131	0.7935
Minim. BASELINE BERT PPL	0.5677	0.4977	14.8686	0.9123	0.0028	0.7928
Minim. BASELINE BERT SLOR	0.5652	0.4980	14.8386	0.9129	-0.0151	0.7926
Minim. BASELINE GPT PPL	0.5752	0.4999	14.9506	0.9122	-0.0017	0.7916
Minim. BASELINE GPT SLOR	0.5717	0.5077	14.5815	0.9136	0.0008	0.7935
Minim. Ranta Length	0.5802	0.5037	15.5895	0.9130	0.0126	0.7794
Minim. Ranta BERT PPL	0.5807	0.5143	15.1632	0.9123	0.0077	0.7720
Minim. Ranta BERT SLOR	0.5865	0.5099	15.6208	0.9132	0.0117	0.7797
Minim. Ranta GPT PPL	0.5759	0.5020	15.3613	0.9120	0.0092	0.7720
Minim. Ranta GPT SLOR	0.5780	0.5005	15.3833	0.9132	0.0141	0.7792
Minim. LOLA Length	0.5722	0.5050	15.5769	0.9133	-0.0005	0.7805
Minim. LOLA BERT PPL	0.5771	0.5137	15.2999	0.9134	-0.0028	0.7769
Minim. LOLA BERT SLOR	0.5811	0.5131	15.3199	0.9133	-0.0006	0.7800
Minim. LOLA GPT PPL	0.5689	0.4995	15.0712	0.9132	0.0048	0.7756
Minim. LOLA GPT SLOR	0.5709	0.4967	15.3573	0.9132	-0.0107	0.7799

Table 3: Performance of the 18 systems against the GGC ground truth references according to the automatic metrics.

nuances, such as negation (Ettinger, 2020), which is crucial for evaluating our task.

5.2 Human Evaluation

We conduct a human evaluation to understand the impact of formulae minimization on the translations. We recruit a group of 42 human evaluators and ask them to give feedback on (i) **comprehensibility** (i.e., whether the message conveyed by the sentence is understandable and not open to multiple interpretations), and (ii) **fluency** (i.e., whether the sentence sounds like a natural English sentence and is grammatically correct). These are central requirements to look for, as text generated from logic can be extremely disfluent and incomprehensible (e.g., a literal translation from a formula), while still being faithful to the input.

Evaluators are asked to rate the comprehensibility and fluency of each translation on a 7-point Likert scale (Likert, 1932). If comprehensibility receives a score < 4 , participants are asked to give the motivations for which the sentence is hard to understand (i.e., ambiguity, complexity, or length of the sentence, or other). See Appendix A for more

information on how we conduct the evaluation and the instructions given to the evaluators.

We sample 48 references from the GGC and select translations of the corresponding formula by 6 systems. The systems we choose are Orig. BASELINE, Orig. **Ranta**, and Orig. LOLA and Minim. BASELINE BERT SLOR, Minim. **Ranta** BERT SLOR, and Minim. LOLA BERT SLOR (henceforth, Minim. BBS, Minim. RBS, and Minim. LBS, respectively; see §4). Among the minimized variants, we choose BERT SLOR for two reasons: (i) BERT-based scoring seems to perform slightly better than the other selection strategies (see §5.1), and (ii) given that SLOR and PPL scores are nearly identical across systems, we opt for SLOR for theoretical reasons (see §4). After the selection, we end up with a total of 48 (references) \times 6 (systems) = 288 experimental items.

Participants and experimental items are randomly assigned to one of six groups and rotated through a 6 (systems) \times 6 (participant groups) Latin square (Fisher, 1925). This guarantees that every item is shown to approximately the same number of participants, that every participant is

shown the same number of items (48), and that participants only see one system translation per original formula.

5.3 Results

The overall comprehensibility and overall fluency of each translation are computed as the means of the ratings given by the evaluators on the two dimensions. The inter-annotator agreements for both dimensions are low (comprehensibility: Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.329$; fluency: Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.282$). We find a very strong positive correlation between the two dimensions (Pearson’s $r = 0.89$; $p \ll 0.001$), indicating that more fluent translations are also more comprehensible.

Figure 1 shows the boxplot with the distribution of the ratings on comprehensibility and fluency for all the systems. The translations from Minim. RBS receive the highest mean on both comprehensibility ($\mu = 5.19$) and fluency ($\mu = 4.89$). One-way ANOVA analyses reveal that for both comprehensibility and fluency, the differences between systems are statistically significant (comprehensibility: $F(5, 282) = 21.72$; $p \ll 0.001$; fluency: $F(5, 282) = 13.39$; $p \ll 0.001$).

Figure 1: Boxplot with the distribution of translations’ mean ratings across systems, for both comprehensibility and fluency.

Tukey’s HSD tests for multiple comparisons show comparable results on the two dimensions. In general, Orig. LOLA is not significantly different from all the minimized variants. This suggests that human evaluators did not perceive a difference between settings where the input was manipulated using equivalence laws (*à la* LOLA) and settings where QBF minimization was used. Moreover, the tests show that all the minimized variants do not significantly differ from each other. This may be

an indication that formula minimization plays an important role beforehand and the choice of the realizer used for translation does not matter much. Lastly, we notice less variance when BERT SLOR variants are involved, especially in comprehensibility with Ranta and LOLA.

We compute correlations between the human ratings and the score assigned by BERTScore, ROUGE-L, and SBERT to the questions rated by the evaluators, for both comprehensibility and fluency. Figure 2 shows the scatterplots and Table 4 the numerical results. The results are comparable across the two dimensions and we find low, but statistically significant positive correlations with human judgments on both comprehensibility and fluency.

Figure 2: Scatterplots with the correlations between translations’ mean ratings on comprehensibility and fluency and scores assigned by the automatic metrics.

	BERTScore	ROUGE-L	SBERT
Comprehensibility	0.331	0.315	0.223
Fluency	0.342	0.302	0.205

Table 4: Correlations between human ratings and automatic metrics on comprehensibility and fluency. All results are computed using Pearson’s r and are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

We shed some light on the reasons why certain translations achieve low comprehensibility by inspecting the responses to the follow-up questions that were presented when comprehensibility is rated poorly (see §5.2). In most cases, low intelligibility corresponds to ambiguities detected in the translation (selected 330 times). Next comes the complexity of the linguistic structure (306), and finally the length of the translation (110). Other reasons are also chosen (118). We break down in Table 5 the detailed figures per system. We clearly

	Orig. BASELINE	Orig. Ranta	Orig. LOLA	Minim. BBS	Minim. RBS	Minim. LBS
Ambiguity	119	56	48	39	33	35
Complexity	110	58	46	38	28	26
Length	46	13	11	14	7	9
Other	33	26	14	15	12	18

Table 5: Figures for the reasons of translations’ low comprehensibility per system.

Sentence	<i>If b is a tetrahedron, then b is a tetrahedron and it is not the case that c is a tetrahedron.</i>
Interpretation 1	<i>(If b is a tetrahedron, then b is a tetrahedron) and (it is not the case that c is a tetrahedron).</i>
Interpretation 2	<i>If (b is a tetrahedron), then (b is a tetrahedron and it is not the case that c is a tetrahedron).</i>
Original Formula	$Tet(b) \rightarrow (Tet(b) \wedge \neg Tet(c))$

Table 6: An ambiguous translation and its possible interpretations.

notice that manipulating the input formula helps improve the comprehensibility of the sentences, as the number of problematic cases decreases with LOLA and the minimized variants. We proceed with a manual check of the translations and report some interesting cases.

A noteworthy example of ambiguity is presented in Table 6. The sentence can have (at least) two interpretations. We need to resort to the original formula in the GGC to disambiguate the sentence and retrieve the intended meaning, which corresponds to the second interpretation. The sentence is generated by Orig. BASELINE. Other systems greatly improve the translation’s comprehensibility, e.g., the corresponding translation by Minim. LBS *b is not a tetrahedron or c is not a tetrahedron* is rated much higher by the evaluators ($\mu = 4.43$ vs. $\mu = 2.86$).

Problematic cases pertaining to the complexity and length of the sentence include those presenting bulleted lists. Evaluators are ambivalent about their use: Some systematically give high scores to sentences containing bulleted lists, while others severely criticize them. One example that particularly baffled the evaluators is the following, as it contains nested levels of indentation:

At least one of these holds:

- *d is a dodecahedron and d is small*
- *all these hold:*
 - *d is not a dodecahedron or d is not small*
 - *a is small*

Further, we inspect in which circumstances formula minimization leads to better translations. We consider the scores on comprehensibility⁹ of the

⁹We get similar results when we look at fluency.

translations by Orig. BASELINE vs. Minim. BBS, and Orig. Ranta vs. Minim. RBS. We select the top 10 instances where the score difference is the highest. We do not consider LOLA to keep the analysis controlled, as LOLA performs further logical manipulation before verbalization. We manually inspect the original and minimized formulae, and find out, unsurprisingly, that the outputs are improved mostly thanks to redundancy removal (e.g., repeated predicates and double negation) from the input. As an example, the GGC formula $\neg(BackOf(c, a) \rightarrow \neg FrontOf(c, e)) \wedge FrontOf(c, e)$ gets translated by Orig. Ranta as *It is not the case that if c is in back of a, then c is not in front of e and c is in front of e*. After minimization, the resulting formula $FrontOf(c, e) \wedge BackOf(c, a)$ gets translated by Minim. RBS as *c is in front of e and in back of a*, gaining 2.71 points in comprehensibility.

6 Conclusion

We have studied the role of brevity in logic-to-text generation. We employed a state-of-the-art (in terms of speed) QBF-based algorithm (Calò and Levy, 2023) that always finds the shortest equivalents to an input PL formula. We verbalized the outputs experimenting with several realizers and selection strategies to study whether the translations from shorter formulae are more comprehensible and fluent than those from their longer logically equivalent counterparts.

The results of our evaluations suggest that manipulating the original input formula (using logical equivalence laws as in LOLA or via minimization) improves the sentences generated. Our study taught us some other lessons as well. For example, the free text comments that our evaluators provided suggest

that there is a need to (i) take measures to mitigate ambiguity in the generated sentences (see also Table 5 and Table 6), and (ii) further improve fluency, despite the fact that both Ranta and LOLA already take some measures to do it (the former performing syntactic optimizations and the latter performing both syntactic and logical optimizations).

In conclusion, is brevity valid as a principle that guides logic-to-text generation? A comparison with referring expressions generation (REG) might be helpful here. Researchers in REG build computational models of the choices that human speakers make when referring. Early REG algorithms (Dale, 1992) always generated the shortest expression that singles out the intended referent. However, such brevity-oriented REG algorithms have been found both computationally infeasible (Dale and Reiter, 1995) and dissimilar to the approaches followed by human speakers. Recent REG models all strike a compromise between brevity and a number of other factors (Van Deemter, 2016); they can be seen as approximating brevity to different degrees. It is conceivable, likewise, that future work on logic-to-text generation ends up following a similar pattern. For example, although the results reported in this paper suggest that brevity has a role to play, future logic-to-text algorithms might achieve even better performance by deviating from brevity to some extent. Perhaps brevity in logic-to-text generation should be weighed less heavily in some communicative situations, just as speakers are known to generate more elaborate referring expressions when referential situations are complex (Koolen et al., 2011; Paraboni and van Deemter, 2014).

We hope that future research, in which logical formulae and their natural language “translations” are embedded in well-understood practical tasks, for example in logic teaching or XAI, may shed further light on these questions.

Limitations

In the present paper, we have concentrated on PL. The first natural extension of this work would be to see if the QBF-based algorithm (or similar methods) could scale up to other (more expressive) formalisms, e.g., first-order logic. This would open up a range of interesting research questions, as in first-order logic, equivalence is in general undecidable. As a first step, an approach based on the use of a first-order theorem prover (e.g., VAMPIRE (Riazanov and Voronkov, 2002)) to check logical

equivalence could be explored. This would not guarantee total coverage but might handle the vast majority of cases.

Our work has focused on four common logical operators, i.e., negation, conjunction, disjunction, and implication. When including other operators, such as the biconditional or the Sheffer stroke, the results could differ. For example, given that the Sheffer stroke is functionally complete on its own, we could have very short formulae but that may result in incomprehensible or disfluent texts.

Our conclusions are drawn from a limited number of realizers sharing similar properties (i.e., all of them are rule-based and derived from the system originally presented in Ranta (2011)). On the other hand, because of this, we were able to perform controlled generation and zoom in on the impact of minimization, which would not be straightforward in other settings, e.g., neural.

Moreover, we have only tackled English as NL. Brevity is drastically language-dependent and experimenting with other (especially typologically diverse) languages could bring different results.

Finally, the evaluation process could be further refined, as hinted by some comments we received in the human evaluation. For instance, some suggest that working within practical domains, especially with the help of pictures, would have eased the work of the evaluators.

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A Details on Human Evaluation

We conduct the human evaluation via Prolific.¹⁰ The 42 evaluators we recruit are all native speakers of English and completed at least high school. They are paid £3 for an estimated workload of 20 minutes. Figure 3 presents the instructions provided to the evaluators and an example sentence.

¹⁰<https://www.prolific.co/>

Thank you very much for participating in this experiment!

It will take approximately 20 minutes to fill in this survey. If you do wish to participate, your response will be handled anonymously: The information in this study will only be used in ways that will not reveal who you are. You will not be identified in any publication from this study or in any data files shared with other researchers. Your participation in this study is confidential. If at any point you would like to stop, you can close this form and your response will be deleted.

I have read the above information and understand the purpose of the research and that data will be collected from me. I agree that data gathered for the study may be published or made available, provided my name or other identifying information is not used.

- I confirm this.
- I do not confirm this and I want to withdraw from participation.

The purpose of the experiment is to assess the quality of some automatically generated English sentences concerning geometrical shapes and their properties. We are interested in receiving feedback on (i) comprehensibility (i.e., do you understand precisely the message conveyed by the sentence?), and (ii) fluency (i.e., does the sentence sound natural to you?).

We will present to you 48 sentences, and for each, we would like to know your feedback on the aforementioned aspects. In detail, you will have to answer the following questions:

1. How **comprehensible** is the sentence? By a comprehensible sentence, we mean that it is understandable and does not have multiple interpretations.
2. How **fluent** is the sentence? By a fluent sentence, we mean that it sounds like a natural English sentence and is grammatically correct.

Please, note down the definitions of comprehensibility and fluency, in case you want to refer to them later.

Here's an example:

Sentence:

If it is not the case that c is a cube, then a is a tetrahedron, and if it is not the case that d is a cube, then b is a cube.

Comprehensibility

①②③④⑤⑥⑦

Fluency

①②③④⑤⑥⑦

Why do you think that the sentence is hard to understand?

(In the real questionnaire, this appears only if comprehensibility < 4)

Note: with 'the sentence is ambiguous', we mean 'the sentence has multiple meanings'.

- The sentence is ambiguous
- The sentence is too long
- The language structure is too complex
- Other:

Now it is your turn!

Figure 3: The instructions provided to the evaluators during our human evaluation.